

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

ESIL Hackathon 2023 Evaluation Report

Prepared by Megan Littrell, Anne Gold, & Emily Ward

University of Colorado Boulder

January 2024

This work is funded by the National Science Foundation.
NSF Award Number DBI-2153040.

Contents

Introduction	4
Program Description	4
Evaluation Methodology	5
Executive Summary	6
Pre-Hackathon Training Evaluation	6
ESIL Hackathon Evaluation (November 15 – 17, 2023)	6
Highlights of the ESIL Hackathon	7
Respondents’ Recommendations for Improvement to the ESIL Hackathon	8
Application Survey Data	10
Participants’ Interests in and Goals for the Hackathon	10
Hackathon Attendee Characteristics	11
Hackathon Attendance and Survey Participation	11
Participant Demographic Information	11
Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation	12
Accommodations for Attendees	14
Attendees’ Personal Hackathon Goals and Expectations	14
Pre-Hackathon Trainings Evaluation	15
Respondents’ Recommendation for Improving Pre-Hackathon Trainings	16
2023 Hackathon Evaluation Outcomes	17
Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL Hackathon	17
Hackathon Overall Highlights	18
Networking Connections and Collaboration	22
Overall Learning and Use of Data Tools and Skills	23
Confidence in Working with Data Skills and Tools	24
	2

Experience Working with Data Cubes	25
Concepts, Data Skills, Tools, and Workflows Acquired	26
Sense of Belonging in the EDS and AI Communities	27
Culture of Inclusion: General Respect and Respect for Expertise	29
Group/Team Dynamics	30
Participant Reflections on the Hackathon Theme	31
Hackathon Overall Impacts and Innovation	32
References	34
Appendix: Evaluation Surveys	35
2023 Hackathon Application	35
2023 ESIL Hackathon Pre-Survey	39
2023 ESIL Hackathon Reflection Survey	49

Introduction

Program Description

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIIL, www.esiil.org) serves as a data science center of excellence and synthesis center that facilitates collaboration across large, diverse teams through the ESIIL Network. ESIIL brings together a diverse community of environmental and biological data scientists to turn environmental and biological data into actionable understanding and knowledge toward a more sustainable society. The center activities support ESIIL's mission: *“Empower an inclusive and diverse community to accelerate continental-scale environmental data science (EDS)”*.

This report summarizes the evaluation feedback on the 2023 ESIIL Hackathon event. The Hackathon is an annual event that aims to address science and application topics identified through the ESIIL Innovation Summit with hands-on, collaborative, and transdisciplinary Environmental Data Science (EDS) work. Each Hackathon event focuses on a key data-science challenge that utilizes a companion, curated data cube with relevant data layers from field, airborne, and satellite sources developed by the ESIIL analytics team. Code developed during the Hackathon will create open, reproducible workflows needed for further refinement into data tools for integration into the ESIIL cyberinfrastructure and for use by the ESIIL Network. The Hackathon aims to bring together people from diverse backgrounds and fields of study and move the field of EDS forward and continue to build the ESIIL community and ESIIL network.

2023 Hackathon. The 2023 Hackathon theme was “Environmental MosAlc: Using AI to put the pieces together.” It was conducted virtually from November 15th – 17th, 2023 with 42 participants from around the world. The Hackathon objectives included:

- Promote inclusion and scientific innovation
- Establish new collaborations across disciplines and sectors to promote community building and knowledge exchange
- Provide training on Environmental Data Science and Artificial Intelligence, and encourage discussions on issues related to data objectivity and sovereignty as well as best practices for responsible use of AI-generated data and models.
- Create purposeful playtime for exploration and evaluation of the environmental data cube curated by ESIIL.
- Facilitate the use of ESIIL's cyberinfrastructure

Pre-Hackathon Trainings. Prior to the event, participants were invited to take part in three two-hour long pre-Hackathon Training webinars designed to help participants begin collaborating with similar levels of background knowledge and skills. The trainings included:

- Cyberinfrastructure & R-Python Bilingualism (10/26/23)
- Environmental Data Science & Data Cubes (11/2/23)
- Artificial Intelligence (11/9/23)

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation team used a collaborative approach (King and Stevahn 2013, Shulha et al. 2016) to design Hackathon evaluation activities, meeting with the Hackathon organizers to discuss survey development prior to the associated events. An online, pre-Hackathon evaluation survey was sent to all registered Hackathon attendees the week before the event. Attendees were reminded about the survey a couple of days before the Hackathon began. On the final day of the Hackathon, attendees were invited to take an online reflection survey to share their experiences of the Pre-Summit and Summit Events. Two reminders were emailed to attendees following the event.

The ESIL staff who organized and facilitated the Hackathon selected the attendees through an online application addressing applicants' experience levels and interest in the specific topics to be investigated at the Hackathon. A subset of applicants were invited to attend the Hackathon event by the facilitators. On the evaluation pre-survey, each attendee was asked if they would give the evaluation team permission to include their application responses in the evaluation of the event. All participants who completed the pre-survey agreed to share their application data for the evaluation. Relevant application data are included in the summary of responses below. Copies of the evaluation surveys are included in the Appendix.

ESIL Program evaluation is co-led by Anne U. Gold, Megan K. Littrell, and Emily Ward. This study has been approved by the University of Colorado Institutional Research Board (IRB) Protocol 23-0162. Funding for this work was provided by the National Science Foundation (NSF, Award #DBI-2153040). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the NSF.

Executive Summary

Pre-Hackathon Training Evaluation

76% of respondents **agreed** that the training on **Cyberinfrastructure & R-Python Bilingualism** and the training on **Environmental Data Science & Data Cube** prepared them for the Hackathon. ¹

41% of respondents **agreed** that the training on **Artificial Intelligence** prepared them for the Hackathon.

To improve these trainings, respondents suggested giving clearer learning objectives ahead of time and using more examples involving environmental applications. They indicated that longer sessions, additional sessions, or additional lessons to complete outside of the trainings could help better prepare them for the Hackathon. Respondents also expressed that a video or manual on CyVerse, or using an alternative platform, would help the sessions to run more smoothly.

ESII Hackathon Evaluation (November 15 – 17, 2023)

95% of respondents expressed that the **Hackathon served as an incubator of ideas** to a Moderate (13%), Large (44%) or a Very Large Extent (38%).

81% of respondents expressed that they were **motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the Hackathon** to a Moderate (31%), Large (31%) or a Very Large Extent (19%).

64% of respondents were **satisfied** with the Hackathon overall.

Sense of Belonging: Respondents felt a statistically significantly stronger sense of belonging in both the EDS and AI communities after the Hackathon compared to before.

Culture of Inclusion: A large majority of respondents (**94-100%**) agreed that colleagues' contributions were **respected and valued**. A large majority of respondents (**88-94%**) also agreed that all group members **felt comfortable providing feedback and contributing opposing viewpoints**.

Group Dynamics:

¹ Icons in the Executive Summary provided by the Noun Project's creators: Ahmad, Chimol, Deylotus Creative Design, Eko Purnomo, IconStock, Nangicon, Rinaros 79, Setyo Ari Wibowo, Siti Nurhayati, and Sundari.

Mentors and Judges: 88% of respondents agreed that their **mentors provided helpful guidance** throughout the Hackathon. 69% of respondents agreed that the **judges provided helpful feedback**, and 63% of respondents agreed that the **judges provided a fair assessment of each group’s project**.

Team Members: 76% of respondents agreed that their **team was effective**. 69% of respondents agreed that their **team had sufficient expertise to meet their goals**.

Networking Connections and Collaboration

88% of respondents (n = 16) **agreed** that they felt better prepared for **community-building and knowledge exchanges** after participating in the Hackathon. **87%** of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections across disciplines and sectors** during the Hackathon.

81% of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections with the EDS community** during the Hackathon.

32% of respondents reported that they had made **connections with the AI community and Community Partners** during the Hackathon.

Highlights of the ESIL Hackathon

Key Themes	Highlights
Training and Learning Opportunities	Appreciation for diversity training, brainstorming training, and learning sessions on topics such as data cubes, environmental datasets, and processing data formats.
Training Facilitation	Recognition and appreciation for effective facilitation during pre-hackathon instruction, emphasizing the importance of guidance and support.
Hackathon Experience	Enjoyment and learning from the hackathon experience, including developing proposals, proving concepts, and working on AI applications for environmental data science.
Data Exploration and Understanding	Learning experiences related to data exploration, understanding data cubes, and discovering publicly available environmental datasets.
Learning about Cyberinfrastructure	Interest in learning about ESIL, its cyberinfrastructure, and gaining knowledge about available resources and capacities.
Networking and Professional Development	Networking opportunities, exposure to machine learning, and involvement in projects are highlighted as positive aspects of the experience.
Building and Working in Teams	Positive experiences in building teams, the opportunity to discuss and imagine projects, and the value of spending time on team-building activities.

Key Themes	Highlights
Global and Interdisciplinary Collaboration	Enthusiasm about collaborating with people around the world and collaborating with people from different disciplines, highlighting the richness of diverse perspectives and skills to address common questions.
Imagining the Impact of Resources	Emphasis on imagining how available resources and capacities can impact the way scientific research is conducted, particularly in the context of environmental data science.
Appreciation for Presentations	Positive feedback on impressive presentations, indicating the value placed on shared insights and knowledge.
Communication and Collaboration Tools	Utilization of communication tools like Slack and an internal website for effective collaboration within cross-disciplinary teams.

Respondents' Recommendations for Improvement to the ESIL Hackathon

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
Proposal Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time constraints were a major challenge in developing the proposal. • Difficulty in formulating a research question within the limited time, leaving little room for data analysis; coding was pushed to time outside the Hackathon schedule. • Lack of experience with AI, leading to uncertainty about selecting an AI model for the proposal.
Team Building and Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial challenges in team building and forming questions. • The first day was challenging to get on task as team members were still learning to communicate with each other. • Encouraging input and participation from all group members was sometimes difficult.
Hackathon Time Commitment & Schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for clearer expectations about the time commitment for the hackathon. • Need for earlier distribution of the schedule so that participants can clear their calendars for full dedication.
Team Dynamics and Technical Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need for a basic level of technological knowledge was emphasized for effective collaboration. • Inclusion was seen as important, but a basic level of understanding was deemed necessary for achieving expected results in a short time. • Some expressed difficulty in understanding some AI/ML techniques.
Time Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management was highlighted as a challenge, especially when coordinating with team members in different time zones. • Participants expressed a desire for more pre-hackathon discussion to better prepare and coordinate efforts within the limited time frame. • Challenges in having sufficient time to build a data cube and interact with data using AI.

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
CyVerse Technical Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Technical trouble working in CyVerse Discovery with Git and GDAL.• Troubleshooting CyVerse environment, including issues with certain R features not working after the team left.• Difficulty with “SSHing”

Application Survey Data

Hackathon participants were asked permission to include data from their Hackathon application as part of the evaluation reporting. All survey respondents agreed to share this information. The table below summarizes common themes for responses to two open-ended questions that : *Why are you interested in participating in the ESIL Hackathon?* And *What do you most hope to gain from this experience?*

Participants' Interests in and Goals for the Hackathon

Key Themes	Summary
Interest in Applying AI to Environmental Research/ Address Environmental Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain hands-on experience, collaborate with experts, and apply AI to real-world environmental challenges. • Use AI for environmental data analysis including: geo-computation, species distribution modeling, predicting disease outbreaks, predicting flooding, and addressing broad ecological questions. • Explore AI's potential for solving environmental problems beyond traditional uses, such as coding assistance. • Learn about and apply rapidly evolving AI tools to address pressing and complex environmental problems. • Incorporating AI tools into upcoming work at participants' institutions. • Develop skills to research and record regional Tribal climate data for sharing across Nations.
Exploring and Applying new Research Tools and Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore new methods, tools, and techniques, including geospatial analysis, Rstudio, machine learning algorithms (e.g., random forest), species distribution modeling, and AI models for segmentation and analysis of environmental data. • Develop better coding, data analysis, and statistical skills and gain exposure to working with large environmental datasets. • Gain experience using AI/ML within data science applications, especially in forming and testing scientific questions for large datasets. • Gain understanding of machine learning and its relevance to data science; integrate machine learning into dissertation projects.
Professional Learning and Career Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop expertise in AI and data analytics to necessary to prepare for careers as data scientists or analysts, especially for early career/PhD student participants. • Interest in developing skills to transition into environmental data science-focused roles.
Collaboration and Networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand data science and AI skill sets through collaboration and networking in an interdisciplinary setting. • Work as a team with diverse backgrounds to enhance problem-solving skills. • Meet professionals with shared interests and develop a sense of community.
Education and Outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in engaging students with real-world data, fostering inquiry-based learning, and incorporating AI/ML tools into student projects.

Key Themes	Summary
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desire to incorporate AI into non-major environmental studies and sustainability classes, and use AI tools and data analysis to enhance middle and high school student learning.

Hackathon Attendee Characteristics

Hackathon Attendance and Survey Participation

Forty-two of the 50 applicants accepted to participate in the Hackathon attended the event. There were 25 respondents for the Summit Pre-Survey (60% response rate) and 18 respondents on the Summit Reflection survey (43% response rate). The Hackathon participants included an international audience with 75% of respondents reporting that they live in the U.S. and 25% reporting that they live outside of the U.S. Survey respondents represented attendees from 10 U.S. States (California, Colorado, Florida, Georgia, Idaho, Illinois, Nevada, New Hampshire, South Carolina, Wisconsin) and 3 other countries (Brazil, Japan, and Germany).

Participant Demographic Information

Survey respondents identified as follows: 60% identified as Women, and the remaining respondents (40%) identified as Men.

Gender Identity	
60%	Women
40%	Men

Most respondents identified as White, Caucasian, European, or European American (60%). Participants also identified as Asian or Asian American (10%); Black, African American, or African (10%); American Indian or Alaska Native (5%); or Hispanic, Latinx, or Hispanic or Latinx American (5%). 5% of respondents preferred not to answer and 5% picked more than one selection for race or ethnicity. No respondents identified as Middle Eastern or North African, Middle Eastern or North African American.

Race and Ethnicity*	
60%	White, Caucasian, European, or European American
10%	Asian or Asian American
10%	Black, African American, or African
5%	American Indian or Alaska Native
5%	Hispanic, Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
5%	I prefer not to answer
5%	More than one selection

5% of respondents identified as having a disability or as being neurodiverse; 10% of attendees preferred not to answer this question. 20% of respondents identified as LGBTQ+; 5% of attendees preferred not to answer this question. There were no respondents who were members of the U.S. Armed Forces. 75% of respondents reported having parents or guardians with a Bachelor’s degree or higher.

Education, Career Experience, and Affiliation

Half of the respondents (50%) had earned a doctoral degree and 30% had a Master’s degree. 20% of respondents had earned a Bachelor’s degree.

Highest Level of Education	
50%	Doctoral degree
30%	Master’s degree
20%	Bachelor’s degree

Field of Study: Attendees were also asked to indicate the field in which they received their highest degree. These degrees encompass a diverse range of academic disciplines, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of Environmental Data Science (EDS), with individuals from a wide array of fields contributing to its advancement and application.

Natural Sciences	Engineering and Applied Sciences	Social Sciences and Humanities	Interdisciplinary & Miscellaneous
Biology	Biostatistics	Curriculum and Instruction (e.g., Physics education)	Public Health
Ecology	Biosystems Engineering	Higher Education	
Environmental Studies	Computer Science	Native American Philosophy	
Evolution	Industrial Engineering		
Marine Sciences (Oceanography; Fisheries & Wildlife)	Mathematics		
	Mechanical Engineering		

Career Stage: The majority of respondents (65%) described themselves as Early Career (0 – 5 years of professional experience or a student or post-doctoral fellow). 20% were Mid-Career (6 – 15 years of professional experience) and 15% were at a Senior stage in their career (more than 15 years of experience).

Affiliation: The majority of respondents reported that they work at an **Academic (higher education) institution (75%)**, followed by **‘Self’ (15%)**. Other respondents reported that they worked at **Non-profit organizations (5%)**, **Private for-profit (5%)**, and **Industry (5%)**.

Academic Affiliations Represented. Of those respondents working at academic institutions, the majority reported affiliation with a Research-Intensive institution (63%). 25% of academic affiliations included institutions serving both undergraduate and graduate students and 6% served primarily undergraduates. One respondent (6%) wrote in State University as their affiliation type and one respondent (6%) chose not to answer. Note that there were no respondents affiliated with Community Colleges, Professional Programs, Tribal College or Tribal-serving institutions, Historically Black Colleges and Universities, Minority-serving Institutions, Hispanic-serving Institutions, or American or Native American Pacific Islander-serving Institutions.

Types of Academic Affiliations*	
63%	Research Intensive
25%	Undergraduate & Graduate students
6%	Undergraduate students
6%	Other
6%	Prefer not to answer

*Respondents selected all that apply. Percentages add up to more than 100%.

Non-Academic Affiliations. 4 respondents (20%) indicated that they *do not* work for an academic institution. These respondents indicated that the main organizations they were affiliated with included a research institute, non-profit and startup, “Location intelligence,” and self-employed.

Primary disciplinary field(s) in Environmental Data Science

(EDS): Hackathon attendees were asked to choose the primary disciplinary field(s) they work in within the broad field of EDS. The most commonly selected EDS fields selected by respondents included **Environmental Science (55%)**, **Computer/Data Science (40%)**, **Biological Science (30%)**, and **Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (30%)**. Fewer respondents represented Math (15%), Engineering (10%), and Geoscience (10%). The majority of respondents selected more than one response as their main field in EDS. Open-ended “Other” responses (15%) included: Ocean Sciences; “Not explicitly in the EDS field;” and STEAM Education.

Primary disciplinary field(s)*	
55%	Environmental Science
40%	Computer/Data Science
30%	Biological Science
30%	AI/Machine Learning
15%	Math
15%	Other
10%	Geoscience
10%	Engineering

*Respondents selected all that apply. Percentages add up to more than 100%.

Professional Society Memberships: The list of memberships comprises a wide range of 27 different professional societies, including those related to Ecology and Environmental Sciences (e.g., Ecological Society of America (ESA)); Geosciences and Earth Sciences (e.g., American Geophysical Union (AGU), National Association of Geoscience Teachers (NAGT)); Mathematics and Statistics (e.g., American Mathematical Society (AMS), American Statistical Association (ASA)); Indigenous, Latinx, and cultural organizations (e.g., International Indian Treaty Council; Oceti Sakowin Treaty; GeoLatinas), and Computer Science and Technology

(e.g., National Association of Computer Science Students (NACOSS)). The societies reported most often included ESA and AGU.

Accommodations for Attendees

On the pre-survey, attendees were asked to describe accommodations needed to make ESIL events as accessible as possible. Ten attendees provided responses to this question. Five respondents indicated they did not need any accommodations. Specific accommodations mentioned by other respondents (n = 5) are summarized below:

- Inclusion of closed captions or written language/transcript to accompany sound on zoom and seating close to speakers for in-person events
- Recorded lectures and/or notes from in-person sessions
- Accommodating more time zones, including APAC region
- Asking participants to list their pronouns
- Providing a laptop, free lodging and flights for in-person events

Attendees' Personal Hackathon Goals and Expectations

On the Hackathon pre-survey, attendees shared 1-3 personal goals they had for the Hackathon. Common themes in their responses are summarized below.

- **Skill Development:** Learning and improving coding skills; Enhancing data wrangling abilities; Acquiring new skills related to environmental data science, machine learning, AI, and cloud computing.
- **Networking and Collaboration:** Building a community or network within the environmental data science sector; Collaborating with colleagues, like-minded individuals, and experts in the field; Making connections with other researchers.
- **Application of Technology:** Exploring and applying AI, machine learning, and data science techniques to environmental data; Understanding and working with large environmental datasets; Learning about data cubes, cloud computing, and data storage in the cloud.
- **Professional Growth:** Advancing career towards environmental data science; Making a meaningful contribution to public health through advanced models and computational techniques; Publishing results and producing products for inclusion in a data science portfolio.
- **Community Engagement:** Staying connected with environmental data science communities; Being part of a team that advances projects and publishes results; Participating in events like hackathons for collaborative learning and problem-solving.
- **Diversity of Perspectives:** Working with people with diverse perspectives and training; Learning perspectives on environmental data science beyond academia.
- **Data Application:** Using large environmental datasets in research and the classroom; Improving flood mapping with remote sensing data.
- **Interest in Specific Tools and Technologies:** Interest in tools like RStudio, Python, Shiny, JupyterLab, Cyverse, Jetstream, GitHub, and GitLab for geospatial data and collaborative coding.
- **Geospatial and Environmental Focus:** Interest in geospatial data and its applications; Focus on environmental and ocean data science.

- **Innovation and Knowledge Sharing:** Fostering innovation in the field of environmental data science; Sharing knowledge and experiences with others.
- **Global Impact:** Contributing to public health research with a global impact, such as disease prediction and monitoring.

Pre-Hackathon Trainings Evaluation

Prior to the Hackathon, attendees participated in virtual pre-Hackathon Trainings, including trainings on Cyberinfrastructure & R-Python Bilingualism; Environmental Data Science & Data Cube; and Artificial Intelligence. On the Hackathon Reflection survey, attendees were also asked to rate how useful each of the trainings were and how well the technical trainings prepared them for the Hackathon, summarized in the graphs below.

94% of Hackathon Reflection survey respondents reported attending the pre-Hackathon trainings.

76% of respondents **agreed** that the training on **Cyberinfrastructure & R-Python Bilingualism** and the training on **Environmental Data Science & Data Cube** prepared them for the Hackathon.

41% of respondents **agreed** that the training on **Artificial Intelligence** prepared them for the Hackathon, while **18%** reported that the training on Artificial Intelligence did not prepare them for the event.

Respondents' Recommendation for Improving Pre-Hackathon Trainings

To improve these trainings, respondents suggested giving clearer learning objectives ahead of time and using more examples involving environmental applications. They indicated that longer sessions, additional sessions, or additional lessons to complete outside of the trainings could help better prepare them for the Hackathon. Respondents also expressed that a video or manual on CyVerse, or using an alternative platform, would help the sessions to run more smoothly. Below are common themes that respondents gave, including some example quotes:

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements	Quotes
Clarify Goals & Learning Objectives	Participants would like better communication about goals and objectives before delving into technical details.	<p><i>"I think a greater emphasis on clear, specific learning objectives would be helpful for orienting participants to the key pieces of insight/knowledge they should keep in mind."</i></p> <p><i>"I think it would be very helpful to have 'big picture' framing ahead of diving deep into tech stuff. E.g. Why is this important? What are we going to learn and why?"</i></p>
Environmental Applications	Participants recommend a focus on environmental applications in AI pre-training, aligning with the ESIII mission.	<p><i>"AI examples that focus on ESIII mission, i.e. geospatial to identify interesting associations."</i></p> <p><i>"AI pre-training should be focused on environmental applications, not on identifying dogs or cats."</i></p>
Pre-Training Time and Resources	<p>Participants acknowledge time limitations and suggest more detailed written tutorial/training materials to aid understanding, especially in condensed sessions.</p> <p>They propose additional coding lessons to deepen understanding and preparation for the Hackathon outside of the trainings.</p>	<p><i>"...there should be more sessions or better distribute the content of them..."</i></p> <p><i>"The data cubes and AI trainings felt too rushed. Having an on-your-own set of lessons to practice some coding would have helped go deeper and feel more prepared going into the hackathon."</i></p>
Cyverse and Tool Usability	Feedback on the CyVerse environment training suggested a desire for a step-by-step manual	<i>"Cyverse was very difficult to use in comparison with other tools like Hex, Google Colab, etc. If the objective is learning, Hex or</i>

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements	Quotes
	<p>and more time for learning and applying techniques.</p> <p>Participants highlighted the importance of user-friendly tools for learning.</p>	<p><i>Colab might be more simple (no SSH connections!)."</i></p> <p><i>"I found the pace of the CyVerse environment trainings to be a bit slow, as I wanted to learn more about using the CyVerse environment and applying some of the machine learning techniques."</i></p> <p><i>"You could provide a step by step manual to log in and access Cyverse before the pre-training, maybe we could use the training sessions with more applied techniques and hands-on in python with machine learning techniques."</i></p>
<p>Appreciation for Pre-training, Interdisciplinary Focus, & Team Construction</p>	<p>Participants appreciated the Hackathon, noting the interdisciplinary nature, team construction, usefulness of training materials, and a positive view of the internal website.</p>	<p><i>"I thought it was a very cool hackathon, loved the internal website, and loved the cross-disciplinary nature of things."</i></p> <p><i>"The teams seemed to be well constructed. I would have liked a time pre-Hackathon to meet the other members of my team before we started working."</i></p>

2023 Hackathon Evaluation Outcomes

Participant Satisfaction with the ESIL Hackathon

64% of respondents were **satisfied** with the ESIL Hackathon overall (29% "Extremely Satisfied;" 35% "Very Satisfied").

The majority of respondents (**74 – 100%**) **agreed** that the various **logistics of the Hackathon were effective** (e.g., Communication, Goals of Sessions, and Agenda). They also overall agreed that the Hackathon was well-organized, engaging, and well-facilitated. However, **18%** of respondents **disagreed** that the **Cyberinfrastructure was easy to use and that the session goals were communicated clearly**.

Thinking about the logistics for the Hackathon, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? (n=17)

Hackathon Overall Highlights

The best parts of the ESIL Hackathon, according to respondents, can be summarized into the following key themes:

Key Themes	Highlights
Training and Learning Opportunities	Appreciation for diversity training, brainstorming training, and learning sessions on topics such as data cubes, environmental datasets, and processing data formats.
Training Facilitation	Recognition and appreciation for effective facilitation during pre-hackathon instruction, emphasizing the importance of guidance and support.
Hackathon Experience	Enjoyment and learning from the hackathon experience, including developing proposals, proving concepts, and working on AI applications for environmental data science.
Data Exploration and Understanding	Learning experiences related to data exploration, understanding data cubes, and discovering publicly available environmental datasets.
Learning about Cyberinfrastructure	Interest in learning about ESIL, its cyberinfrastructure, and gaining knowledge about available resources and capacities.

Key Themes	Highlights
Networking and Professional Development	Networking opportunities, exposure to machine learning, and involvement in projects are highlighted as positive aspects of the experience.
Building and Working in Teams	Positive experiences in building teams, the opportunity to discuss and imagine projects, and the value of spending time on team-building activities.
Global and Interdisciplinary Collaboration	Enthusiasm about collaborating with people around the world and collaborating with people from different disciplines, highlighting the richness of diverse perspectives and skills to address common questions.
Imagining the Impact of Resources	Emphasis on imagining how available resources and capacities can impact the way scientific research is conducted, particularly in the context of environmental data science.
Appreciation for Presentations	Positive feedback on impressive presentations, indicating the value placed on shared insights and knowledge.
Communication and Collaboration Tools	Utilization of communication tools like Slack and an internal website for effective collaboration within cross-disciplinary teams.

Themes from the responses regarding to what extent the Hackathon met participants' expectations and where it did not are summarize with some representative quotes:

Met Expectations:

- Interdisciplinary collaboration
- Training provided was appreciated
- Internal website with sample code and data sets available.

Didn't Meet Expectations:

- Cyverse did not meet expectations.
- Learning new AI concepts fell short.
- Less time for coding than expected.

Example Quotes:

- *"The technical training was incredible, and the experience of working closely with a team was wonderful. I would say that my knowledge about cyberinfrastructure grew tremendously, but not my knowledge of AI."*
- *"I expected to learn new things and I did. I did not expect to have so much time to work with others developing questions and talking about things we were interested in, and honestly having that time*

was amazing and made the work even more relevant and important and something I want to see through rather than me saying "that was a fun workshop" and closing the windows."

- *"I think I had expected a little more training during this experience than I received. You can only do so much with the limited time, so I understand. However, near the end, I felt that I would have been more prepared/gained more from the experience if I already had knowledge on using environmental data, geospatial data, and AI."*
- *"The Hackathon met my expectations in terms of teaching me about cyberinfrastructure and data cubes. I would have appreciated more time being allocated to how AI can be applied to data cubes and environmental questions."*
- *"Met expectations: cross-disciplinary, diversity training, brainstorming training, internal website with sample code and data sets; Didn't meet expectations: Cyverse, learning new AI concepts"*
- *"I think I made the common mistake of assuming that the purpose of the hackathon was coding-based. We spent a lot of time working on getting data together and less on developing our exact research question and refining a presentation. Looking back, it would have been better for our scores if we had spent far less time in the Cyverse and far more time on Google Slides and looking through the literature."*

In a final open-ended question, respondents shared additional feedback on the ESIL Hackathon. Themes and representative verbatim responses are included below:

Positive Feedback:

- **Appreciation for the Event:** Participants expressed gratitude and thanked the organizers, stating that it was great and wonderful.
- **Positive Remarks on Organization:** Positive feedback on the overall job, with a request to continue the program and facilitate the use of provided resources. Positive remarks on the setup and schedule of the event, indicating satisfaction with the organizational aspects.
- **Optimistic Outlook on Effort:** Acknowledgment that the event involved hard work, coupled with optimism that it will improve over time.
- **Importance of Dedicated Project Discussion Time:** Recognition of the importance of having dedicated time to discuss projects within teams, indicating a positive aspect of collaboration.

Feedback on Improvements:

- **Challenges Encouraging Group Participation:** One participant mentioned the challenge of encouraging participation from all members of their group, highlighting a potential area for improvement in group dynamics.
- **Suggestion for Extended Duration:** A suggestion was made to extend the event's duration, proposing a 4-day total event format with 2 days in one week and two days in another. This could be seen as a potential area for improvement.

- **Desire for More Coding-Related Final Product:** A suggestion for future hackathons to have the final product more related to data and coding, as opposed to a presentation. This indicates a preference for a more hands-on, practical approach.
- **Zoom Fatigue Acknowledged:** Recognition that experiencing Zoom for three consecutive days can be challenging. While not overtly negative, it highlights a potential area for improvement in terms of participant well-being.
- **Request for Step-by-Step Manual:** A desire for a step-by-step manual on how to log in to Cyverse and use it before pre-training sessions, indicating a need for clearer instructions.

Respondents' Recommendations for Improvement to the Hackathon

Hackathon participants shared the most challenging parts of the Hackathon.

Key Themes	Recommended Improvements
Proposal Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time constraints were a major challenge in developing the proposal. • Difficulty in formulating a research question within the limited time, leaving little room for data analysis; coding was pushed to time outside the Hackathon schedule. • Lack of experience with AI, leading to uncertainty about selecting an AI model for the proposal.
Team Building and Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial challenges in team building and forming questions. • The first day was challenging to get on task as team members were still learning to communicate with each other. • Encouraging input and participation from all group members was sometimes difficult.
Hackathon Time Commitment & Schedule	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for clearer expectations about the time commitment for the hackathon. • Need for earlier distribution of the schedule so that participants can clear their calendars for full dedication.
Team Dynamics and Technical Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need for a basic level of technological knowledge was emphasized for effective collaboration. • Inclusion was seen as important, but a basic level of understanding was deemed necessary for achieving expected results in a short time. • Some expressed difficulty in understanding some AI/ML techniques.
Time Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time management was highlighted as a challenge, especially when coordinating with team members in different time zones. • Participants expressed a desire for more pre-hackathon discussion to better prepare and coordinate efforts within the limited time frame. • Challenges in having sufficient time to build a data cube and interact with data using AI.
CyVerse Technical Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical trouble working in CyVerse Discovery with Git and GDAL. • Troubleshooting CyVerse environment, including issues with certain R features not working after the team left. • Difficulty with "SSHing"

Networking Connections and Collaboration

88% of respondents (n = 16) **agreed** that they felt better prepared for **community-building and knowledge exchanges** after participating in the Hackathon. **87%** of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections across disciplines and sectors** during the Hackathon.

81% of respondents indicated that they felt they had made **connections with the EDS community** during the Hackathon. However, only **32%** of respondents felt that they had made **connections with the AI community** during the Hackathon.

Respondents were asked if they made any new professional connections during the Hackathon (n=12).

83% of respondents indicated that they **made professional connections at the Hackathon, mainly with the members of their project group**. 17% indicated that they did not make new connections, but were hopeful about doing so in the future. Example quotes include:

- *Yes. I'm excited to do some more of our proposed work. We are planning on a meeting to discuss it further. I really enjoyed working with all the different people in our group and getting everyone's expertise and opinions.*
- *No yet! But hopefully in the future.*

- *Yes - at the very least, I really appreciated connecting with the people in my group. I do feel like these could be highly relevant professional connections.*
- *My team is still in contact and we are seriously considering collaborating on a paper. This is very exciting to me.*

Overall Learning and Use of Data Tools and Skills

The majority of respondents (**81%**) agreed that they **made use of ESIL’s Cyberinfrastructure** during the Hackathon.

There was lower agreement on the following topics:

69% of respondents agreed that they **learned about the benefits of AI and best practices for it’s responsible use**, while 19% were neutral and 13% disagreed.

63% of respondents **agreed** that their **awareness of data sovereignty increased**, while 25% remained neutral and 13% disagreed.

56% of respondents **agreed** that they **had opportunities for purposeful playtime for EDS exploration**, while 31% remained neutral and 13% disagreed.

19% of respondents **agreed** that they had opportunities to work with AI models. However, **62% disagreed** and 19% were neutral.

In an open-ended question, respondents were invited to elaborate on the previous question. 9 respondents include comments. Their verbatim responses are listed below:

- *Spent lots of time trying to help group do SSH*
- *Hard to pursue data sovereignty at same time of learning how to work with big open data resources. it seems data sovereignty might require a different type of meeting with more leadership from Indigenous data scientists associated with and beyond ESIL. I am thinking of [names of ESIL Leadership members redacted] as well as other leaders who were at first summit.*
- *I got the first exposure to ESIL resources which I plan to explore them further.*
- *Again, I'm still a bit unclear on how to use AI. I think I understand AI models a bit better, but I still don't know how to input the data and actually run the model. I think it's something I have to try with my own data before it'll be really clear to me. However, I recognize that this it a complicated topic.*
- *I would honestly have enjoyed a week-long Hackathon to better build those new relationships and collaborations with my team.*
- *I think it is a very good idea of ESIL to create or promote an IA and ESD community after the Hackathon and facilitate the means through the Slack channel, the Google group and the access to the platform.*
- *I had difficulty in using the cyverse environment.*
- *great opportunity to collaborate, did not get a ton of AI experience*
- *Benefits and best practices of AI seems kinda to be sidelined by the goal for formulating this as an "AI question"*

Confidence in Working with Data Skills and Tools

Respondents were asked to reflect on their confidence before and after the Hackathon. They self-reported **higher confidence** after the Hackathon in **Working with data cubes**, **Creating reproducible workflows** and **Collaborating with new people**.

Regarding coding and AI work, respondents' confidence increased from before to after the Hackathon for **Envisioning the future of EDS research with AI** and slightly increased for **Documenting code so that others can use it**.

Most respondents also expressed an increase in confidence in **Coding with other people** and **Running code in the cloud**. However, a small percentage of respondents ~6% indicated a decrease in confidence for both topics.

[Experience Working with Data Cubes](#)

Participants were asked to “Please comment on the quality of the data cube, for example whether it was comprehensive, inspiring, useful, etc.” Common themes in participant responses are summarized below:

Positive Feedback and Excitement:

- Participants shared positive feedback and excitement about the concept of data cubes.
- Some participants found the idea of data cubes aligning with their previous research and teaching experiences, generating enthusiasm.

Challenges in Implementation:

- Several participants faced challenges in implementing data cubes, citing technical difficulties, time constraints, or obstacles in using specific tools like RStudio.
- Limited time during the Hackathon was a common constraint mentioned, affecting the depth of engagement with data cubes.

- Specific difficulties were mentioned, such as the complexity of working with geospatial data and issues in converting between reference systems.

Appreciation for Resources:

- Appreciation was expressed for resources such as ESIL's pre-gathered data and the data library website.
- Participants acknowledged the value of a data library in overcoming challenges related to identifying available datasets.

Desire for Continued Exploration:

- Participants expressed a desire to continue working with data cubes and explore their potential further.

Integration with AI and Technical Complexity:

- Interest was shared in integrating data cubes with AI, recognizing the potential synergy.
- Technical challenges were mentioned, including difficulties in modifying trainings with new variables and challenges in working with geospatial data and reference systems.

Need for Python Integration:

- Some participants expressed a preference for Python over R for working with data cubes, citing more tools and specific packages available for integration with AI.

Concepts, Data Skills, Tools, and Workflows Acquired

Participants were asked to “Please describe any new concepts, data skills, tools, or workflows that you learned about throughout the Hackathon (if any).” Responses (n = 14) are summarized into themes below:

Interdisciplinary Collaboration:

- Multiple participants highlighted the valuable experience of working with interdisciplinary and diverse groups with varying expertise. This also sparked interest in further collaboration.

Introduction to Cyberinfrastructure:

- Participants expressed being introduced to cyberinfrastructure, gaining insights into cloud/remote computing resources, and linking them to GitHub.

Spatial Data Skills:

- Participants highlighted learning about spatial data workflows, including making predictions using AI with spatial data in R.
- Use of R for spatial data tasks, such as querying, trimming, clipping, and creating maps, was emphasized.

Data Cubes and Remote Sensing:

- Recognition of the importance of data cubes, especially in the context of remote sensing data.
- Learning concepts related to data cubes, harmonizing datasets, and utilizing platforms like CyVerse for remote sensing tasks.

Machine Learning Techniques:

- Exposure to and learning about various machine learning techniques was mentioned, contributing to a better understanding of AI applications.
- Specific mentions of using virtual environments to code (CyVerse) and different AI coding tools.

Sense of Belonging in the EDS and AI Communities

Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were conducted to evaluate changes in attendee's the pre-survey and reflection survey responses about sense of belonging. There were 11 respondents with matched pre- and post-responses included in the analysis.

Before and after the Hackathon, attendees were asked to choose the picture that best described their “the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of an Environmental Data Science (EDS) professional.” Results showed a significant change such **that attendees saw a greater overlap between themselves and EDS professionals at the end of the Hackathon** compared to before the Hackathon, $Z = 2.72$, $p < .001$.

Attendees were also asked to rate the extent to which they agreed with statements about their sense of belonging in the EDS and AI communities. There was a **significant increase** in respondents' agreement with “I

belong to the EDS Community” ($Z = 2.41, p < .05$) and with “Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity” ($Z = 2.79, p < .01$), shown in the figure below.

There was also a significant increase in respondents’ agreement with “I belong to the AI Community” ($Z = 2.74, p < .01$) and with “Being an AI community member is an important part of my identity” ($Z = 2.09, p < .05$), shown in the figure below.

Culture of Inclusion: General Respect and Respect for Expertise

A large majority of respondents agreed that **colleagues' contributions were respected and valued (94-100%)**. A large majority of respondents (**88-94%**) also agreed that all group members **felt comfortable providing feedback and contributing opposing viewpoints**. However, 6% indicated that they disagreed.

A large majority of respondents (**88 – 100%**) agreed that individually they **felt respected by colleagues, their contributions and expertise were respected and valued, they felt comfortable providing feedback and sharing opposing viewpoints, and they handled disagreements constructively.**

Group/Team Dynamics

Mentors: 88% of respondents agreed that their **mentors provided helpful guidance** throughout the Hackathon.

Judges: 69% of respondents agreed that the **judges provided helpful feedback**, and **63%** of respondents agreed that the **judges provided a fair assessment of each group’s project** with 38% remaining neutral.

Team Members: 76% of respondents agreed that their **team was effective**, however 13% within this group remained neutral and 13% disagreed. **69%** of respondents agreed that their **team had sufficient expertise**, however 19% within this group remained neutral and 13% disagreed.

Participant Reflections on the Hackathon Theme

The 2023 ESIL Hackathon theme was Environmental MosAIC: Using AI to put the pieces . Participants were asked to comment on their thoughts about the use of AI in the field of Environmental Data Science before and after the event. Below is a summary of there responses before and after the Hackathon with some representative quotes from respondents:

Before the Hackathon, respondents generally expressed optimism and belief in the potential of AI in Environmental Data Science (EDS). Participants highlighted the importance of AI in addressing complex environmental challenges, extracting patterns from large datasets, and making better predictions. There was enthusiasm about the opportunities AI presents for advancing scientific processes, especially in the context of climate science and climate change efforts. However, there were also cautious sentiments, with concerns about the ethical implications, potential biases, and the need for thoughtful and intentional applications of AI in EDS. Example quotes from the responses are below:

- *AI will be a critical tool for solving challenging environmental problems. I believe that there are many use-cases where we can apply AI in EDS.*
- *I think it's [AI] got a lot of power to help us make better predictions and to better understand and visualize really large data.*
- *I am excited by the capability of AI in EDS to deepen understanding around environmental challenges and think the potential of AI in EDS to address environmental issues is incredibly promising.*

- *At this point, I have a resigned / cautious approach to AI in EDS from a generative AI/LLM perspective. I think that getting some training and familiarity with the tools is important since things are moving quickly...However, there's still a lot of uncertainty in implementation as well as ethical concerns.*
- *Current belief is that AI is overhyped as an analysis tool. I worry that moving from analysis based on stronger mathematical theory to black-box information systems will result in new problems with interpretations and bias.*

After the Hackathon, the responses become more specific and practical. Participants expressed intentions to use AI in their work, with a desire for more concrete examples and hands-on applications. Some participants reflected on the challenges they faced in formulating research questions and suggested a more structured approach in future Hackathon events, integrating training sessions with practical applications. There was a mix of increased understanding and acknowledgment of remaining gaps in knowledge. Participants still recognize the value of AI, but may have a more nuanced view, acknowledging the need for responsible AI practices and emphasizing the importance of addressing biases in training data. Example quotes from the responses are below:

- *I plan to use it [AI].*
- *I will use [AI] for sure.*
- *I think I understand it [AI] more now. It is also the piece I still want to work on and learn because I can see its value and want to learn enough to teach my students how to use it.*
- *I am in favor of the use of responsible AI in EDS. I believe that ESILL is very thoughtful and proactive about the responsible and inclusive use of AI and AI development in EDS.*
- *We need to put a lot of thought into preparing the training data to prevent biases.*

Hackathon Overall Impacts and Innovation

The Hackathon as an Incubator of Ideas: **95%** of respondents expressed that the **Hackathon served as an incubator of ideas** *To a Very Large Extent* (38%), *To a Large Extent* (44%), or *To a Moderate Extent* (13%) with an additional 6% indicating *To a Small Extent* and none *To a Very Small Extent*.

When asked to elaborate on this rating, respondents (n = 11) expressed both positive experiences and challenges during the ESILL hackathon. While some appreciated the collaborative aspect and the exposure to new datasets, methodologies, and ideas, there were also concerns about the ownership of intellectual property by the US government. The collaborative environment provided opportunities to address knowledge gaps and learn from team members. Despite not generating many new research ideas, participants gained valuable skills and insights into data processing. Some teams focused more on product creation than data analysis, leading to a perceived gap in achieving expected results. The hackathon was generally seen as an excellent opportunity for ideation and collaboration, with engaging discussions and valuable feedback from judges influencing project directions. Example quotes are included below:

- *I think that many gaps of knowledge that I had for some struggles I faced during the hackathon were filled by members of my group. This was very helpful in facilitating my understanding.*
- *There were a lot of different ideas that came up during our discussions, and a lot are worth some follow-up work.*
- *...did not love finding out mid-way that the US govt would own IP, but nonetheless*
- *My team was more focused on creating a product than actually analyzing data. Therefore, I consider that the expected results were not achieved in part.*
- *Feedback from judges was very helpful in seeing the different ways our project could go.*

Motivation to Continue Working on Ideas: **81%** of respondents expressed that they were **motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the Hackathon** *To a Very Large Extent* (19%), *To a Large Extent* (31%), or *To a Moderate Extent* (31%), with another 6% indicating *To a Small Extent* and 13% *To a Very Small Extent*.

Future Plans (n =13): Participants were asked to comment on how they plan to use what they learned at the Hackathon in their future work. Some respondents expressed excitement about ideas and intellectual property (IP), but also expressed uncertainty due to concerns about the US government's ownership of IP. Others indicated that their continued involvement depends on group outreach and potential integration with other working groups. Challenges with time constraints and formulating research questions were highlighted, which led to limited data analysis and reduced motivation to continue post-hackathon. However, there was a desire to explore AI models, leverage resources like Cyverse, and apply newfound knowledge. Example quotes are provided below:

- *excited about ideas/IP but not sure about pursuing since US govt owns them?*
- *Depends on outreach from group; I would continue if they are interested, and see ways it might merge with 1-2 other WGs. It is a valuable project, but my involvement is from methods side and I hope to continue with a working group that submitted proposal on 1 Nov.*
- *Due to limited time and a struggle to formulate a research question, my group had little time for data analysis. We also struggled to understand which AI algorithm should be used for our question. By the end, we only were able to accomplish a minimal amount of work for the proposal. Because of this, and the spread of my group members around the world, we didn't have much of a desire to continue working on the project after the hackathon, in the case that we did not win.*
- *I really want to try out the AI model on our project to see how it works.*
- *I plan to take advantage of the Cyverse more in the future.*
- *I learned more about working in the cloud, which has been very scary and intimidating for me.*
- *interested in using more ML in my work*

References

- King, J. A., & Stevahn, L. (2012). *Interactive evaluation practice: Mastering the interpersonal dynamics of program evaluation*. Sage Publications.
- Shulha, L. M., Whitmore, E., Cousins, J. B., Gilbert, N., & al Hudib, H. (2016). Introducing evidence-based principles to guide collaborative approaches to evaluation: Results of an empirical process. *American*

Appendix: Evaluation Surveys

2023 Hackathon Application

Virtual Hackathon - Track I Application

Environmental MosAlc is [ESIL's 2023 Hackathon](#). Join us to learn, collaborate, and use artificial intelligence (AI) to address environmental challenges in a respectful and inclusive environment.

In addition, this opportunity includes:

- Networking
- Training on environmental data science
- Training on artificial intelligence
- Training on cyberinfrastructure
- Connecting with funding agencies and community partners
- Resources to address challenges in environmental biology

Environmental MosAlc comes in two designs: Track I and Track II.

- Are you new to coding or AI?
- Are you an AI expert who wants to learn about environmental challenges?
- Are you interested in exploring the potential of a huge environmental data cube?
- Would you like to meet new collaborators and connect with funding agencies and community partners?

If you answered "yes" to any of these questions, **Track I** is for you! Please keep reading and fill out this application.

Not sure? Check out [Environmental MosAlc - Track II](#).

When is the event?

November 15-17, 2023.

What will we ask you to do?

Join a team of environmental scientists, data experts, and coders, to explore the data sets, propose a scientific question that can be addressed with all or some of the data sets, frame the question as an AI problem, and present your proposal to a panel of experts.

What are we offering?

We'll provide mentors, a data cube with environmental data for the globe, cyberinfrastructure, data science training, and technical support.

All teams will receive feedback from a panel of experts from organizations, academics, and other community partners. **The best proposal will receive a financial award to meet one time in person in Boulder, CO (via [ESIL's working groups](#)) as well as cyberinfrastructure, and technical and scientific support to complete their project.**

Important Dates:

October 26: Pre-hackathon webinar on environmental data science

November 2: Pre-hackathon virtual training on AI

Nov 9: Pre-hackathon virtual training on CI

Applications are due September 22. Successful applicants will be informed by October 6.

If you have any additional questions, needs, or concerns, please contact Virginia Iglesias at Virginia.Iglesias@colorado.edu.

This Hackathon is funded by the National Science Foundation (via award # DBI-2153040), and subject to the NSF's terms and conditions.

This form is automatically collecting emails from all respondents.

First Name*

Last Name*

Email address*

Cell phone number

Current affiliation*

Please select the option that best represents your sector.*

Other...

If you are currently affiliated with an academic institution, please select the category that best describes your institution.*

Other...

Please select the career stage that best represents you.*

Other...

Why are you interested in participating in the ESIIL Hackathon?*

What environmental data have you engaged with?*

Do you have expertise or experience in any of the following domains? (Select all that apply)*

Other...

What kinds of data do you have experience working with?

Other...

Describe any of your prior work involving data-intensive science and analysis.

On what scales do you currently conduct research or work?

Other...

Please describe how you as an individual would contribute to the diversity of the working group (optional).

What do you most hope to gain from this experience?*

SURVEY

Please answer the below questions to help us understand our audience.

Please rate your experience working with the following tools, or your familiarity with the following subject areas.

Description (optional)

R & R Studio*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Python & Jupyter Notebooks*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Data cubes*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Git & GitHub

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Theoretical basis of remote sensing*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Artificial Intelligence (AI)*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Integrating / fusing diverse datasets and data types*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Please rate your commitment to open science (efforts to increase accessibility, transparency, and collaboration within scientific fields)*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

Please rate your commitment to open science (efforts to increase accessibility, transparency, and collaboration within scientific fields)*

I've never used this tool.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

I'm a power user and use this tool on a regular basis

2023 ESIL Hackathon Pre-Survey

ESIL Innovation Summit participants were selected based on their ability to help build the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community of the future. **Understanding the thoughts and opinions of Innovation Summit participants is therefore crucial.** Please fill out the information below to the best of your ability.

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: *We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.*

What is your name?

How did you learn about the ESIL Hackathon? Select all that apply.

- I attended the ESIL Innovation Summit in May, 2023.
- I received an email from ESIL@colorado.edu.
- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- ESIL's website
- Word of Mouth - I heard from others about it
- An online forum or Slack channel (e.g. ECOLOG, AISES); if so, which one: _____

Other: _____

What would you like to get out of your participation in the ESIL Hackathon? Please share 1-3 goals or expectations you have for the Hackathon.

The Hackathon theme focuses on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Environmental Data Science (EDS). Please share your current thoughts about the use of AI in EDS.

You completed an application for the Hackathon event that included questions about your expertise and expectations for the event. Is it okay with you if we include your application responses in this evaluation study? (Data will be de-identified after the data collection period ends.)

Yes

No

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					

I belong to the AI Community.

Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.

Being an AI community member is an important part of my identity.

ESIIIL holds inclusion as a core principle and method for diversifying environmental data science at a time when society needs all perspectives, and science needs to serve all. The questions below invite you to provide demographic information that will help us better understand who currently participates in ESIIIL activities and events and will inform our approaches to inclusion to better serve ESIIIL’s mission. You are never required to provide this information. All questions contain a “Prefer not to answer” option.

Which of the following best describes your current career stage?

- Early Career (I am an undergraduate student, graduate student, post-doctoral fellow, or have 0 to 5 years of professional experience.)
- Mid-Career (I have 6 to 15 years of professional experience.)
- Senior (I have more than 15 years of professional experience.)
- Other. Please describe. _____
- Prefer not to answer

What best describes the organization in which you work?

- K-12 or Informal Education
- Academic (higher education)
- Government: Federal
- Government: State
- Government: Local
- Non-profit: Research and Development (FFRDC/National Labs/etc)
- Non-profit: other
- Private for-profit
- Industry
- Self
- Other: _____
- Prefer not to answer

Are you affiliated with an academic institution?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = Yes

With which type of academic institution are you affiliated? Select all that apply.

- Community College/ 2-yr College
- Professional Program
- Tribal College or Tribal-Serving Institution (TCU)
- Historically Black University (HBCU)
- Minority Serving Institution (MSI)
- Hispanic Serving Institution (HSI)
- American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institutions (AAPISI)
- Primarily Undergraduate Serving
- Undergraduate and Graduate Serving
- Research Intensive (R1/R2/etc)
- If none of the options fit, how would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

- Prefer not to answer

Display This Question:

If Are you affiliated with an academic institution? = No

How would you describe the main organization you are affiliated with?

Which of the following categories best describe your highest level of education?

- Some high school
- High school diploma or equivalent
- Vocational training
- Some college
- Associate degree (e.g. AA, AE, AFA, AS, ASN)
- Bachelor's degree (e.g. BA, BBA, BFA, BS)
- Some graduate work
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MBA, MFA, MS, MSW)
- Applied or professional graduate degree (e.g. MD, DDS, JD)
- Doctoral degree (e.g. EdD, PhD)
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

In what field did you receive your highest degree?

What are the main professional societies to which you belong? Please select up to 5 professional societies from the drop-down menu, or type in the organization's full name if it is not listed.

- Professional Society #1
- Professional Society #2
- Professional Society #3
- Professional Society #4
- Professional Society #5

In which disciplinary field(s) of Environmental Data Science do you MAINLY work? Select all that apply.

- Environmental Science
- Computer/Data Science
- Social Science
- Economics
- Geoscience (Geology, Geography)
- Biological science
- Engineering
- Math
- Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
- Other. Please specify. _____

We collect demographic information for three reasons: 1) to hold ourselves accountable for meeting our diversity goals, including to provide opportunities for voices that may not have been well represented in Environmental Data Sciences; 2) to ensure that ESIL meets the needs of a national community; 3) to be able to share aggregated, non-identified data in publications and reports; and 4) to conduct basic research on the social dynamics and outcomes of scientific

collaborations and teams. You are never required to provide this information. All questions contain a "Prefer not to answer" option.

How do you currently describe your gender identity? Select all that apply.

- Woman
- Man
- Transgender
- Non-binary
- Gender non-conforming
- I identify as: _____
- I prefer not to answer

Do you identify as LGBTQ+?

LGBTQ+ includes (but isn't limited to) Agender, Aromantic, Asexual, Bisexual, Gay, Gender fluid, Gender non-conforming, Genderqueer, Intersex, Lesbian, Non-binary, Pansexual, Queer, Questioning, Trans, and Two spirit.

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

Please select the racial/ethnic group(s) with which you identify. Select all that apply.

- Black, African American, or African
- American Indian or Alaska Native
- Asian or Asian American
- White, Caucasian, European, or European American
- Hispanic or Latinx; Hispanic or Latinx American
- Middle Eastern or North African; Middle Eastern or North African American
- Pacific Islander or Native Hawaiian
- Not listed, please specify: _____
- I prefer not to answer

We realize the above options for describing your racial and ethnic identity are not all inclusive. If you would like, you can tell us how you would prefer to describe your racial and ethnic identity.

Do you identify as having a disability or as being neurodiverse?

Disability/neurodiversity status includes (but is not limited to) those who are Deaf or have serious difficulty hearing; Blind or have serious difficulty seeing even when wearing glasses; those who have serious difficulty walking or climbing stairs; those with a serious disability related to a physical condition; those with a serious disability related to a mental or emotional condition, or those with known conditions of neurodiversity.

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

To help us develop ESIL so that the project is as accessible as possible, please describe any accommodations that would be needed for you to participate optimally in virtual and in-person events:

Are you a member of the U.S. Armed Forces?

- Yes, I am currently serving
- Yes, I am a Veteran
- No, I am not a member of the U.S. Armed Forces
- I prefer not to answer

Have either of your parents or guardians completed a Bachelor's degree or higher (Masters, PhD)?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer

Where do you live?

- I live in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:) _____
- I am outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?) _____
- I prefer not to answer

Where is your place of work located?

- Place of work is in the United States (If yes, please specify your home zip code:) _____
- Place of work is outside the United States (If yes, in which country are you located?) _____
- I prefer not to answer

2023 ESIL Hackathon Reflection Survey

We would like to invite you to share your feedback on the ESIL Hackathon. Your participation in the survey is optional, but your feedback is greatly appreciated. Your responses will be summarized and shared with the organizers to facilitate improvements to future events. The survey will take approximately 5 - 10 minutes to complete.

What is your name?

To what extent do you agree or disagree that the following pre-Hackathon Trainings prepared you for the Hackathon?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	I did not attend this event.
Virtual Training on Cyberinfrastructure & R-Python Bilingualism (October 26)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Virtual Training on Environmental Data Science & Data Cube (November 2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Virtual Training on Artificial Intelligence (November 9)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

In what ways could the pre-Hackathon Trainings be improved?

What were the best parts about the ESIL Hackathon?

What were the most challenging parts of the ESIL Hackathon?

Overall, how satisfied were you with the ESIL Hackathon?

- Extremely Satisfied
- Very Satisfied
- Moderately Satisfied
- Slightly Satisfied
- Not at all Satisfied

In which ways did the Hackathon meet your expectations and in which ways did it not?

The Hackathon theme focused on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Environmental Data Science (EDS). Please share your thoughts about the use of AI in EDS after participating in the Hackathon.

Thinking about the logistics for the Hackathon, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Communication about the meeting was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meeting was well-planned	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Goals of sessions were clearly communicated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Meeting was well-facilitated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Agenda was well-designed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speakers and presenters were engaging	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Cyberinfrastructure (CI) was easy to make use of	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using Slack helped the meeting to run more smoothly	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about the outcomes of the Hackathon overall, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about this event?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	N/A
I created new connections across disciplines and sectors.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I made connections with the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I made connections with the AI community.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I made connections with community partners.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am better prepared for community-building and knowledge exchange through new collaborations.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had opportunities for purposeful playtime for Environmental Data exploration at the Hackathon.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I used of ESIL's Cyberinfrastructure during Hackathon.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I learned about the benefits of AI and best practices for responsible use of AI.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I worked with AI models.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I increased my awareness of data sovereignty.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please elaborate on your responses to the previous question.

As part of the Hackathon, you worked with an ESIL data cube. Please comment on the quality of the data cube, for example whether it was comprehensive, inspiring, useful etc.

We are interested in learning about how your participation in the ESIL Innovation Summit is shaping your perception of yourself as a member of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community. Select the picture that best describes the current overlap of the image you have of yourself and your image of the Environmental Data Science (EDS) community.

Please indicate to what extent you agree with the following statements.

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neutral	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree	N/A
I belong to the EDS community.	<input type="radio"/>					
I belong to the AI Community.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an EDS community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					
Being an AI community member is an important part of my identity.	<input type="radio"/>					

Please describe any new **concepts, data skills, tools, or workflows** that you learned about throughout the Hackathon (if any).

Please provide two responses for each statement to tell us **how confident you feel** in doing these tasks independently **AFTER you finished participating** in the Hackathon **compared to BEFORE participating** in the Hackathon.

	CONFIDENCE AFTER				CONFIDENCE BEFORE			
	Very Confident	Moderately Confident	Slightly Confident	Not Confident	Very Confident	Moderately Confident	Slightly Confident	Not Confident
Working with data cubes	<input type="radio"/>							
Creating reproducible workflows	<input type="radio"/>							
Collaborating with new people	<input type="radio"/>							
Coding with other people	<input type="radio"/>							
Documenting code so others can use it	<input type="radio"/>							
Running code in the cloud	<input type="radio"/>							
Envisioning the future of EDS research with AI	<input type="radio"/>							

Thinking about the ESIL **Hackathon overall**, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Colleagues showed a general respect for one another	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Colleagues respected the expertise of others in the group	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The contributions of all group members were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
All group members felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Disagreements were handled constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The meeting code of conduct was consistently implemented	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Slack was an effective way to communicate with peers and work more efficiently	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thinking about **your own experiences** during the Hackathon, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I felt respected by my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Others in my group respected my expertise	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt my contributions were valued	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable providing an opposing viewpoint or interpretation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I handled disagreements constructively	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
My team worked well together	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My team was effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My team has sufficient expertise to meet our goals	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The mentor(s) provided helpful guidance for my team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Judges provided fair assessments of each group's project	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The feedback judges provided was helpful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Have you made new connections or research collaborations during the Hackathon? If so, please elaborate.

To what extent did the Hackathon serve as an incubation of ideas?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

Please elaborate on your answer to the previous question.

To what extent are you motivated to continue working on the ideas that were explored during the Hackathon?

- To a Very Large Extent
- To a Large Extent
- To a Moderate Extent
- To a Small Extent
- To a Very Small Extent

How do you plan to use what you learned at the Hackathon in your future work?

Please share any other feedback you have about the Hackathon.
